

Role of Phosphate and Organic Matter in the Management of Lateritic Soils for Increasing Productivity

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Laterites and lateritic soils occupy large areas in the states of West Bengal, Bihar and Orissa. The pH of these soils range from 5.0 to 6.5 or even less. They are poor in calcium, organic matter, available phosphate and exchangeable bases. Due to poor return many of these have gone out of cultivation and hence their proper management for increasing crop production has a vital bearing on the agricultural economy of the respective states.

The utility of phosphates in crop production, when mixed with decomposing organic matter has been advocated. As such, a large number of field trials were conducted extending for over 3 to 10 years in the lateritic soils of West Bengal with phosphate and organic matter. It has been found that a mixture of all kinds of organic matter along with phosphatic fertilizers is best suited for the management of lateritic soils by enriching the soil nitrogen, decreasing their acidity, saving the leaching away of lime and supplying available phosphate and calcium.

NEXT to nitrogen, phosphorus is one of the most essential nutrient required for proper plant growth. In all chemical and biochemical reactions taking place in soil, phosphates present, or added play an important role in maintaining soil productivity. Phosphates have got real value in crop production when these are mixed with decomposing organic matter since their use stimulates the nitrogen fixing bacteria, both symbiotic and non-symbiotic to greater activity^{1,2}. In our country, the supply of phosphatic fertilizers has been mainly in the form of bone meal. Basic slag, a bye-product of steel industry, is also a source of phosphate but the total and available phosphate of the indigenous product is low. Large deposits of rock phosphates have also been found in our country.

Indian soils show considerable variation in their physical, chemical and microbial character due to widely diverse parent materials, topography and climatic conditions. Good results have been obtained when phosphate along with decomposing organic matter has been used than using either of them alone.

An attempt has been made in this paper to discuss the physico-chemical role of phosphatic fertilizers and organic matter in the management of lateritic soils for increasing crop production.

Characteristic of lateritic soils :

Laterites and lateritic soils of tropics have developed on rocks of very ancient origin. These are weathered due to high temperature and intermittent dry and moist climate. The land of these places is usually undulating and soil erosion has taken place, Iron concretions are dispersed on the surface and honey comb vascular structured lateritic beds containing oxides and hydroxides of

iron and aluminium are present in the subsurface region of the profile. Iron and aluminium rich clay sometimes hardens to different degree of hardness due to dehydration caused by high temperature with intermittent dry and wet climate. In West Bengal laterite and lateritic soils occur in the districts of Birbhum, Bankura, Midnapore and parts of Burdwan.

Laterite and lateritic soils are light textured and porous. Due to leaching of bases they are acidic in nature (pH ranges from 5.0 to 6.5 or even less) and are poor in calcium, organic matter, available phosphate and exchangeable bases. Kaolinite is the predominant clay mineral of such soils having exchange capacity of the order of 3 to 12 me/100 g of soil. Due to poor return, many of these soils have gone out of cultivation and hence proper management of these soils for increasing productivity has a vital bearing on the agricultural economy of the respective states where these soils occupy large areas.

Physical and chemical compositions of some typical lateritic soils of West Bengal are presented in Table 1. Some field experiments were carried out for a number of years using phosphatic fertilizers (both water soluble and water insoluble) with and without organic matter specially in laterite and lateritic soil regions of West Bengal in order to find out sustained effect of these treatments on crop yield.

Effect of phosphatic fertilizer (water soluble) mixed with decomposing organic matter :

In lateritic soil regions of Midnapore and Suri (Birbhum) in West Bengal superphosphate was applied with and without organic matter (wheat straw, cow dung and water hyacinth) and the yield

TABLE 1—MECHANICAL AND CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF SOIL SAMPLES (PERCENTAGE ON OVEN DRY BASIS)

	Suri (Birbhum) (lateritic sandy loam)	Midnapore (Laterite)
Coarse sand	30.14	12.56
Fine sand	32.06	28.32
Silt	20.02	35.80
Clay	18.06	23.34
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.06	1.94
Al ₂ O ₃	5.42	3.98
CaO	0.27	0.15
P ₂ O ₅	0.05	0.04
Ex. Ca (% me)	4.38	3.18
Total bases (% me)	12.05	4.15
Total-C	0.35	0.26
Total-N	0.06	0.04
pH	5.7	5.8

TABLE 2—AVERAGE YIELD OF PADDY GRAIN IN Q/ha

Treatment	Midnapore		Suri (Birbhum)	
	Paddy yield	% increase in yield over control	Paddy yield	% increase in yield over control
1. No manure	12.7	—	14.4	—
2. Organic matter (12.5 tonne/ha)	16.4	29.1	18.3	27.0
3. Super phosphate (50 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha)	13.8	8.7	15.6	8.3
4. Organic matter + superphosphate (2+3)	16.8	32.2	18.9	31.3

of paddy was recorded year after year. The experiment was continued for 3 years. The average results obtained are given in Table 2.

Similar results were obtained in another lateritic soil region at Sriniketan (Birbhum) after continuing the experiment for 6 years by the application of 33.7 kg and 67.4 kg P₂O₅ per ha in the form of superphosphate in combination with 10 tonnes per ha of farm yard manure (see Table 3).

TABLE 3—AVERAGE YIELD OF PADDY GRAIN IN Q/ha

Treatment	Paddy yield	% increase in yield over control
1. Control	15.6	—
2. 33.7 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	23.5	50.6
3. 67.4 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	24.1	54.5
4. 10 tonne F.Y.M./ha	18.9	21.2
5. 33.7 kg P ₂ O ₅ + 10 tonne F.Y. M.(2+4)	25.8	65.4
6. 67.4 kg P ₂ O ₅ + 10 tonne F.Y.M.(3+4)	27.2	74.4

After the end of the above two experiments physical and chemical analysis of the soils of experimental plots were carried out. Marked improvements in the physico-chemical properties of these soils were observed. It, therefore, shows that application of water-soluble superphosphate either alone or in combination with organic matter/F.Y.M. not only increases the crop yield but also results in an improvement in the physico-chemical properties of the soil.

Effect of phosphatic fertilizer (water insoluble) mixed with decomposing organic matter :

Experiment was conducted at lateritic soil region, Suri (Birbhum), with water insoluble phosphatic fertilizers like bone meal in combination with and without application of farm yard manure. The experiment was conducted for 12 years. The results are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—AVERAGE YIELD OF PADDY GRAIN IN Q/ha

Treatment	Paddy yield	% increase in yield over control
1. Control	23.6	—
2. 22.4 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	25.6	8.5
3. 44.8 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	25.9	9.7
4. 10 tonne F.Y.M./ha	28.5	20.8
5. 22.4 kg P ₂ O ₅ + 10 tonne F.Y.M. (2+4)	30.5	29.2
6. 44.8 kg P ₂ O ₅ + 10 tonne F.Y.M. (3+4)	34.3	45.4

In this case also marked improvement in the physico-chemical properties of the soil was observed after 12th year of the experiment. It is therefore concluded that in lateritic soil, application of water insoluble phosphates like bone meal, which is mainly tricalcium phosphate, either alone or in combination with farm yard manure can increase the crop productivity and at the same time improve the physico-chemical properties of such soils.

Effect of phosphate on the loss of lime by leaching :

Lateritic soils contain much less exchangeable calcium in the exchange complex. Hence attempt should be made to prevent loss of lime due to leaching from these soils and decrease their lime requirement for increasing productivity. Burgess³ reported decrease in lime requirement of soil and increase in crop yield by the application of both water soluble phosphate (superphosphate) and water insoluble phosphates (rock phosphate, ground bone, thomas slag etc.). Treating lateritic acid soils by rock phosphate or bone meal containing calcium and phosphate is always better than by the application of calcium carbonate. This is due to the fact that the solubility of CaHPO₄, which is formed in sufficient quantity on the addition of rock phosphate or bone meal to these types of soils, is less than Ca(HCO₃)₂ formed on the addition of CaCO₃. Hence leaching of calcium compounds from such soil is certainly less than when Ca₃(PO₄)₂ is added to soil instead of CaCO₃. Moreover, both calcium and phosphate ions are made available from rock phosphate or bone meal while from CaCO₃ only calcium is made available.

Residual effect of phosphates :

Residual effect of superphosphate has been studied in lateritic soil region at Sriniketan (W. Bengal). Superphosphate was applied continuously for five years and the residual effect was noted in the sixth year. The results are recorded in Table 5. These results clearly indicate that application of

phosphatic fertilizers in lateritic soils has also residual effect which is beneficial for the succeeding crop. Hence it can be inferred that the fertility of soils is sustained specially by the use of phosphatic materials.

TABLE 5—INCREASE IN YIELD OF PADDY GRAIN OVER CONTROL IN Q/ha

Location	Doses of phosphate	
	33.7 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	67.4 kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha
Sriniketan (Lateritic soil)	+2.48	+1.11

Effect of phosphate and organic matter on the fixation and loss of nitrogen from soils :

Ghosh⁴ reported marked increase in the nitrogen content of soil when organic material like starch undergoes slow oxidation in presence of phosphate. Similar results were also obtained by Dhar and coworkers⁵ by using straw, water hyacinth, coal etc, as organic matter and phosphate. These authors⁵ further reported retardation of the loss of nitrogen when ammonium sulphate was applied to soil along with phosphate.

The observations recorded here, some extending for more than 10 years, clearly reveal that phosphatic fertilizers (both water soluble and water insoluble) like superphosphate, bone meal, rock phosphate, basic slag etc. in presence of decomposing organic substances in lateritic soils can enrich the nitrogen content of these soils, decrease their lime requirement and also leave residual effect for the next crop.

From all these considerations it can be concluded that a mixture of various kinds of organic matter along with phosphatic materials is best suited for the management of lateritic soils by enriching the soil nitrogen, decreasing their acidity, saving the leaching away of lime and supplying available phosphate, calcium and trace elements for increasing plant growth. In general, for getting maximum benefit for water insoluble phosphate fertilizers, it is desirable to incorporate these materials along with organic matter 1½ to 2 months before the sowing of crop so as to mix them well with lateritic acid soils while for water soluble single, double or triple superphosphate it is preferable to place these fertilizers preventing as far as possible to mix with the existing soil so that they can be quickly taken up by crops and are not fixed in soil. It is, therefore, evident that application of a mixture of phosphatic fertilizers and organic matter play a big role in the management of lateritic soils and this should be advocated for increasing crop production and maintaining fertility of these soils.

References

1. G. H. COLLINGS, "Commercial Fertilizers", IV Edn., 1947, p. 393.
2. E. J. RUSSELL, "Soil Conditions and Plant Growth", 1932, p. 554.
3. P. S. BURGESS, Rhode Island Agr. Expt. Station Bull., 1922, p. 189.
4. S. K. GHOSH, "Mother Earth", Jour. Soil Association, England, July 1955.
5. N. R. DHAR and CO-WORKERS, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1956, 25, sec A, part 4.